

METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Pr (III), La (III) and Sm (III) METAL IONS COMPLEXES WITH HYDROXY SUBSTITUTED CHALCONE PH-METRICALLY

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Abstract

In the present work, we have investigated the proton-ligand stability constants and metal-ligand stability constants of ligand 1-(5-bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl)-5-phenylpenta-2,4-dien-1-one (L_3) with Inner transition metal ions like Pr (III), La (III) and Sm (III), which were determined pH-metrically at 0.1 M ionic strength. ($30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$) in a 70% dioxane-water mixture by the Bjerrum method as adopted by Calvin Wilson. 1:1 and 1:2 complexes were formed between 1-(5-bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl)-5-phenylpenta-2,4-dien-1-one (L_3), Pr (III), La (III) and Sm (III). The values of pK and log k were evaluated and compared with the resultant data.

Keywords: Substituted chalcone, Dioxane – water mixture, stability constant.

Introduction

Chalcones are organic compounds with a basic structure consisting of two aromatic rings linked by a three-carbon α , β -unsaturated carbonyl system. Substitution of hydroxyl groups on the aromatic rings introduces a range of unique chemical and biological properties. Hydroxy-substituted chalcones are particularly important due to their applications in medicinal chemistry, including antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant activities.

The stability of metal-ligand complexes plays a significant role in understanding the coordination chemistry of chalcones with metal ions. These metal-ligand complexes have potential applications in various fields such as catalysis, biological systems, and materials science. One of the most effective ways to study these complexes is through the determination of their stability constants.

The stability constant of a complex is a quantitative measure of the strength of the interaction between a metal ion and a ligand. It provides insight into the affinity between the two components, and larger stability constants indicate more stable complexes. Understanding the stability constants of hydroxy-substituted chalcones is important for predicting the behaviour of these complexes in different chemical environments.

For hydroxy-substituted chalcones, metal-ligand complexation typically involves coordination through the hydroxyl groups and carbonyl oxygen.

A significant contribution was made to the field of stability constants of organic ligands

and their metal complexes by Bjerrum¹ and Calvin². Ayesha et al reported the transition metal complexes comprise a central metal ion surrounded by coordinated organic ligands, together forming versatile scaffolds with diverse biochemical applications. The identity of the metal center and its oxidation state alongside the ligands within the coordination sphere enable extensive tuning of structural, electronic, and chemical properties. This has facilitated growing interest in transition metal complexes for therapeutic and diagnostic applications as metallodrugs or imaging agents. A key consideration underlying development effort is quantifying metal complex stability. The stability constant reflects equilibrium binding affinity between the metal and ligands, with higher values indicating tighter interactions and more stable complexes. Multiple interdependent effects related to ligand denticity, geometry, electron configurations, solvation, entropy changes, kinetics, and reaction conditions all influence stability.³ Jagtap's study examined the stability constant of Ni (II) with substituted pyrazole carboxylic acid derivatives at 298K in a 70% DMF-water mixture.⁴ The interaction of metal ions Fe(III), Mn(II), Cr(III) and Ti(III) with substituted 2-oxo-2H chromene-3-Carbohydrazide derivatives at 0.1 M ionic strength are determined by pH metric technique. Calvin Bjerrum titration technique is used to study proton ligand and metal ligand stability constant. It is observed that there is formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. The log K1 and log K2 values are found out for simultaneous complex formation.⁵ Thakur et al.⁶ studied the stability constant of Schiff bases with lanthanum using

pH metric titration and the Calvin-Bjerrum method. They calculated thermodynamic parameters like Gibb's free energy change, entropy change, and enthalpy change. Thorat et al.⁷ studied the complex formation between Pr (III) and Sm (III) metal ions and 3-(2-hydroxy-3-nitro-5-methylphenyl)-5-(3-nitrophenyl) isooxazoline, 4-chlorophenyl isooxazoline, and 2-furyl isooxazoline. R.P. Giram et al. have been studied the stability constants and thermodynamic parameters of transition metal complexes of substituted aminothiazole Schiff bases.⁸

The study investigated the interaction of metal ions with the organic ligand N-[(E)-(4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl) methylene] isonicotinohydrazide. The ligand was synthesized using an anti-mycobacterial agent and aromatic aldehydes. The formation of these ligands was confirmed through various tests, with the stability constants arranged in a specific order.⁹

Experimental methodology**Material and Methods**

All chemicals used are AR-grade. The ligand (L_3) was synthesized in the laboratory by the reported protocol¹⁰. The stock solution of the ligand was prepared by dissolving the required amount of ligand in a 70% (dioxane and water) mixture.

General procedure**pH-Metric Method for Determining Stability Constants**

The pH-metric method is widely used for the determination of stability constants of metal-ligand complexes due to its simplicity, accuracy, and effectiveness. This method involves monitoring the pH changes of a solution containing both the ligand (hydroxy-substituted chalcone) and the metal ion as they undergo complexation in the presence of a titrant, typically a strong acid or base.

By carefully measuring the pH during the titration, the degree of protonation or deprotonation of the ligand can be tracked, allowing the determination of complex formation equilibria. The stability constants of the resulting metal-ligand complexes are then calculated using various techniques, such as the Bjerrum or Irving-Rossotti methods.

Types of Titrations

Free acid HNO_3 (0.01 M)

Free acid HNO_3 (0.01 M) and ligand ($20 \times 10^{-4}\text{M}$)

Free acid HNO_3 (0.01 M) and ligand (20×10^{-4}) and metal ions ($4 \times 10^{-4}\text{M}$) against a standard 0.1N NaOH solution. The ionic strength of all the solutions was maintained at 1M by adding the appropriate amount of KNO_3 solution. All the titrations were carried out in a 70% (dioxane and water) mixture, and the readings were recorded for each 0.1 ml addition. The graph of the volume of alkali added (NaOH) against pH was plotted. The ligand involved in the present work may be considered a monobasic acid having only one dissociable H^+ ion from the phenolic OH group, and it can therefore be represented as HL. The dissociating equilibrium can be shown as.

By the law of mass action, we have,

$$K = \frac{[\text{HL}]}{([\text{H}^+][\text{L}^-]} \quad (1)$$

Where, the quantities in bracket denote the activities of the Species at equilibrium.

Result and Discussion

Calculation of Proton-Ligand Stability Constant (n_A)

The plots between the volume of NaOH and the pH of the solution were used to determine the proton ligand stability constant (representing the replacement of H⁺ ions from the functional group of the ligand with respect to the pH value). The horizontal difference ($V_2 - V_1$) was measured accurately between the titration curves of free acid and acid + ligand. It was used to calculate the formation number n at various pH values and a fixed ionic strength $\mu = 0.1$ M using Irving and Rossotti's equation [1, 2].

$$n_A = \gamma \frac{(E_0 + N)(V_2 - V_1)}{(V_0 + V_1) TL^0} \quad (2)$$

Where V^0 is the initial volume of the solution. E^0 and T_L^0 are the initial concentrations of the mineral acid and ligand, respectively. V_1 and V_2 are the volumes of alkali of normality N during the acid and ligand titration at a given pH. γ is the replaceable proton in the ligand. The data on n_A obtained at various pHs, along with the horizontal difference for some representative systems, are represented in Table 1. The metal ligand ligand formation number (n) is estimated by Irving-Rossotti's equation.

$$n = \frac{(E_0 + N)(V_3 - V_2)}{(V_0 + V_2) Tm^0} \quad (3)$$

Where the notations have the same meaning as given in the earlier equation. The horizontal difference ($V_3 - V_2$) between the metal complex (A+M+L) and reagent (A+L) curve is used to evaluate the value of n using Irving Rossotti's equation.

Table 1 Proton ligand stability constant (pK)

Ligand	System	pK	
		Half integral method	Point wise method
L3	1-(5-bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl)-5-phenylpenta-2,4-dien-1- One	7.7871	6.4506

Table 2: Metal-ligand stability constant (log K)

System	LogK ₁	LogK ₂	Δ LogK
Pr (III)+L ₃	4.6788	2.4522	2.2266
La (III)+L ₃	5.1819	2.5028	2.6791
Sm (III)+L ₃	5.5230	3.3126	2.2104

Conclusion

From the titration curves, it is observed that the departure between the acid-ligand (A+L) curve and the acid-ligand-metal (A+L+M) curve for all systems started at pH 3.6. This indicated the commencement of complex formation. Also, the change in color from yellow to orange in the pH range from 3.9 to 8.6 during titration showed the complex formation between metal and ligand.

The differences between LogK₁ and LogK₂ is less than 2.5, indicating the simultaneous formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. When the difference is greater than 2.5, a stepwise complex formation takes place.¹¹ From Table 2, it is observed that in the systems Pr (III) + L₃ and Sm (III) + L₃, the difference between log K₁ and log K₂ is sufficiently small, which indicates the simultaneous formation of complexes between metal ions and ligands takes place. While in system La (III) + L₃, the difference between log K₁ and K₂ is greater than 2.5, indicating stepwise complex formation between metal ion and ligand takes place.

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